

IMPROVING THE SPEECH OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN
LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES OUTSIDE THE CLASSROOM.

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Annotation: This article provides an explanation of the semantic meaning of the word exercise, its conceptual basis, its use in educational tools and its characteristics, the role and importance of exercises in the development of linguistic, speech, and basic competencies from scientific and methodical sources. , the scientific opinions and views of linguists and Methodist scientists were analyzed.

Key words: exercise, speech skills, development of speech forms, development of oral and written speech, forms of speech, written literacy, norms of literary language, knowledge, skills, skills, speech styles, speech skills, speech competence, dictionaries, lexical layer, work on text types, text analysis.

In the following years, one of the main tasks is to teach pupils and students foreign languages on the basis of innovative approaches and advanced modern technologies, as well as to create knowledge, skills, skills and speech on the subject. Through the use of innovative technologies in teaching foreign languages to students, their thinking, having certain ideas, speaking and speaking skills in a foreign language are developed. According to McCarthy, "the methodology of teaching foreign languages is half a century old

developed a lot during It has been carried out at various times in grammatical translation, audio-linguistic structure, global audiovisual, inductive/deductive, functional, ideational, situational, communicative, immersion, learning/acquiring, recommendation, etc. as it is organized with linguistic tools, it becomes easier for them to master and understand the topic. Therefore, as a result of using these tools in the course of the lesson, the ability to remember the semantic meaning of words in memory, recall and use a number of words in live speech develops.

Raising the interest of young students in learning a foreign language, creating opportunities for them, and supporting them will help them learn this language faster need:

- providing the lesson with various electronic resources;
- creating methodical literature for use in foreign language teaching activities;
- focus on individual work with students;
- increase the effectiveness of the quality of education;
- adequate introduction of new educational technologies into the educational process;
- organizing and motivating students during the lesson.

The role and importance of exercises and assignments along with a number of educational tools in the methodology of teaching a foreign language to students in the course of the lesson is of great importance.

It is known that the exercise has been used since ancient times to conduct classes and teach the subject, this educational tool is considered one of the sources that make students think and

learn the subject. In particular, during the teaching of the German language and in the implementation of the goals of the lesson, the advantages and important aspects of the exercise are distinguished. This educational tool is widely used in the subject of education to clearly understand and strengthen the subject. Ya. Kamensky emphasized the importance of exercise in his work "The School of Pansophia" and wrote: "Exercise makes a person skillful, dexterous, aware of everything, interested in all fields, suitable for any job". In fact, as a result of performing exercises, various psychological characteristics of students improve. The textbook "Native language didactics" compiled by a number of scientists led by O. Ochilov contains the following information about the importance of linguistic exercises: "Linguistic exercises are a component of the process of preparing young people for life, the leading factor in the implementation of language education"¹ Linguistic exercises o develops students' linguistic competences. Expressed his thoughts on the systematization of assignments. If exercises and assignments are effectively used to improve the quality and efficiency of education in foreign language teaching, if foreign language is taught from easy to complex, students' knowledge and skills will develop, they learn the given topic perfectly and develop their speech literacy.

In her research, A. Nisanbayeva focuses on exercises and tasks related to the development of text-based speech in primary grades. Developing speech based on the text, if the teacher consistently works on exercises and tasks starting from the primary grades, the students' speech will develop well. In our opinion, the exercise is a set of independent activities that establish the essence of educational content and develop speech forms. The exercise is considered an educational tool that improves the student's knowledge and develops speaking skills for learning a foreign language.

I.M. Podgaetskaya thinks as follows about the performance of exercises and assignments: "methodological interest is an emotional feeling that makes students want to know the knowledge of the subject and stimulates enthusiasm for this subject. "Attitude is understood. From the outside, this attitude is manifested in diligence and curiosity."

So, if we pay attention to the teaching of exercises and assignments among the main educational tools in the course of the lesson, we will increase their interest in learning this subject. their speaking and writing competences will develop and grow if special exercises and exercises developed by the teacher are used to learn a foreign language even more deeply at the required level.

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